

A simple method for simultaneous estimation of Wiener (W) and Szeged (Sz) indices of benzenoids

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Abstract : This paper describes a simple method for the simultaneous estimation of Wiener (W) and Szeged (Sz) indices for benzenoid systems using elementary cut method. The method is extended to cyclic graphs containing acyclic (tree-like) side chains.

Keywords : Topological index, benzenoid systems, cyclic graphs, elementary cuts.

A topological index is a single number, derived following a certain rule, which can be used to characterize the molecule¹. It is one of the widely used molecular (graph theoretical) descriptors. Recently, more informative definition of molecular descriptor is given², which is applicable to topological index as well. This definition reads as : "The molecular descriptor is the final result of a logical and mathematical procedure which transforms chemical information encoded within a symbolic representation of a molecule into an useful number or the result of some standardized experiment". A plethora of topological indices have been proposed so far³⁻⁶. The Wiener index (often also called the Wiener number) W is the first, oldest, and widely used topological (graph-theoretical) index. Even today it is widely used in Quantitative-Structure-Property/Activity/Toxicity Relationship (QSPR/QSAR/QSTR) studies. This index was introduced in 1947 by Harold Wiener⁷ as the path number. The path number was introduced for alkanes and is equal to the number of carbon-carbon bonds between all pairs of carbon atoms in an alkane.

The Wiener index (W) was modified for cyclic graph by Gutman^{8,9} and this new index was called the Szeged index and denoted by Sz . This index is based on distances in the molecular graph but is not of the same type as the Wiener index (W). For acyclic systems Sz and W coincide.

Several methods have been proposed for the calculation of W and Sz indices^{10,11}. The method of the estimation of topological indices should be as simple as possible, accurate, and less time consuming.

Gutman and coworkers^{12,14} have designed an algorithm for the calculation of the Wiener and the Szeged indices of benzenoid hydrocarbons based on the examination of their elementary cuts. The expressions used for such calculations are given below :

$$W(B) = \sum_c nB'(c)n(B''(c)) \quad (1)$$

$$Sz(B) = \sum_c r(c)n(B'cc)n(B''(c)) \quad (2)$$

These summations are going over the complete set of elementary cuts (CSEC). Here, B' and B'' are the fragments of benzenoid system B .

The examination of the aforementioned algorithms promoted us to propose a simple method for the simultaneous calculation of Wiener (W) and Szeged (Sz) indices of benzenoids. We have then extended the method for the calculation of W and Sz indices for cyclic graphs containing tree-like (acyclic) side chains. The methodology is described below.

Experimental

The details of obtaining fragments B' and B'' of the benzenoid B , from elementary cuts are given earlier by

Gutman and coworkers¹²⁻¹⁴, and, therefore, they are not given here.

The method for the simultaneous calculations of W and S_z indices of benzenoid system consists of obtaining three summations : Σ_1 , Σ_2 , and Σ_3 resulting from CSEC. The Σ_1 is the result of the sum of the products of vertices belonging to B' and B'' ; Σ_2 is the sum of edges involved in the process of CSES; and Σ_3 is the product of Σ_1 and Σ_2 . Obviously Σ_1 and Σ_3 respectively gives the W and S_z indices of benzenoid system under consideration :

Elementary cut C	$n(B')$	$n(B'')$	r	$r.n(B').n(B'')$
C_1	n'_1	n''_1	r_1	$r_1.n'_1.n''_1$
C_2	n'_2	n''_2	r_2	$r_2.n'_2.n''_2$
C_3	n'_3	n''_3	r_3	$r_3.n'_3.n''_3$
\vdots	\vdots	\vdots	\vdots	\vdots
C_n	n'_n	n''_n	r_n	$r_n.n'_n.n''_n$
$\Sigma_1 = \Sigma_n(B').n(B'')$		$\Sigma_2 = \Sigma_r$	$\Sigma_3 = \Sigma r.n$	
$= W$		$= \text{Total edges in } B$	$= S_z$	

Here, n'_1, n'_2, \dots, n'_n and $n''_1, n''_2, \dots, n''_n$ are the number of vertices in the fragments B' and B'' generated by the elementary cuts C_1, C_2, \dots, C_n . Similarly, r_1, r_2, \dots, r_n are the number of edges involved in the elementary cuts C_1, C_2, \dots, C_n respectively.

We illustrate this method of simultaneous calculation of W and S_z taking the cyclic graph representing benzene as below :

Fig. 1. All elementary cuts of benzene.

This graph has three elementary cuts : C_1, C_2 and C_3 . Therefore, applying the aforementioned methodology we obtain :

Elementary cut C	$n(B').n(B'')$	r	$r.n(B').n(B'')$
C_1	$3 \times 3 = 9$	2	18
C_2	$3 \times 3 = 9$	2	18
C_3	$3 \times 3 = 9$	2	18
$\Sigma_1 = 27$		$\Sigma_2 = 6$	$\Sigma_3 = 54$
$= W$		$= \text{Total edges}$	$= S_z$

Thus, from the molecular graph we obtained $W = 27$ and $S_z = 54$.

Results and discussion

Applications to benzenoid systems :

We now illustrate the efficiency of our method considering the cases of polyacenes, fibonacenes, helicenes, and polyphenylenes.

Case of polyacenes :

The straightforward calculations of W and S_z indices for polyacenes uses the following expressions :

$$W(L_n) = 1/3 (16h^2 + 36h^2 + 26h + 3) \quad (3)$$

$$S_z(L_n) = 1/3 (44h^2 + 73h^2 + 43h + 3) \quad (4)$$

Use of these expressions for the polyacene L_3 in Fig. 2 gave $W = 279$ and $S_z = 656$.

Fig. 2. Molecular graph of polyacene L_3 .

The methodology used by us gives the same values of W and S_z for L_3 as illustrated below :

Fig. 3. All elementary cuts of L_3 .

Elementary cut C	$n(B').n(B'')$	r	$r.n(B').n(B'')$
C_1	$3 \times 11 = 33$	2	$2 \times 33 = 66$
C_2	$7 \times 7 = 49$	2	$2 \times 49 = 98$
C_3	$11 \times 3 = 33$	2	$2 \times 33 = 66$
C_4	$7 \times 7 = 49$	2	$4 \times 49 = 196$
C_5	$3 \times 11 = 33$	2	$2 \times 33 = 66$
C_6	$7 \times 7 = 49$	2	$2 \times 49 = 98$
C_7	$11 \times 3 = 33$	2	$2 \times 33 = 66$
$\Sigma_1 = 279$		$\Sigma_2 = 16$	$\Sigma_3 = 656$
$= W$		$= \text{All edges}$	$= S_z$

Case of fibonacenes (zig-zag polyacenes) :

The expressions used for the calculation W and S_z indices of fibonacenes (zig-zag polyacenes) are as

below :

$$W = 1/3 (16h^3 + 24h^2 + 62h - 21) \quad (5)$$

$$S_z = 1/3 (40h^3 + 60h^2 + 107h - 45) \quad (6)$$

Thus, giving $W = 271$ and $S_z = 632$ for the fibonacenes F_3 . Our methodology, as illustrated below, also gives the same values of W and S_z for F_3 (Fig. 4).

Fig. 4. All cuts of fibonacenes F_3 .

Elementary cut C	$n(B').n(B'')$	r	$r.n(B').n(B'')$
C_1	$3 \times 15 = 45$	2	$2 \times 45 = 90$
C_2	$3 \times 15 = 45$	2	$2 \times 45 = 90$
C_3	$5 \times 13 = 65$	3	$3 \times 65 = 195$
C_4	$5 \times 13 = 65$	3	$3 \times 65 = 195$
C_5	$7 \times 11 = 77$	2	$2 \times 77 = 154$
C_6	$7 \times 11 = 77$	2	$2 \times 77 = 154$
C_7	$13 \times 5 = 65$	3	$3 \times 65 = 195$
C_8	$15 \times 3 = 45$	2	$2 \times 45 = 90$
C_9	$15 \times 3 = 45$	2	$2 \times 45 = 90$
$\Sigma_1 = 529$		$\Sigma_2 = 21$	$\Sigma_3 = 1253$
$= W$		All edges	$= S_z$

Elementary cut C	$n(B').n(B'')$	r	$r.n(B').n(B'')$
C_1	$3 \times 11 = 33$	2	$2 \times 33 = 66$
C_2	$3 \times 11 = 33$	2	$2 \times 33 = 66$
C_3	$5 \times 9 = 45$	3	$3 \times 45 = 135$
C_4	$9 \times 5 = 45$	3	$3 \times 45 = 135$
C_5	$11 \times 3 = 33$	2	$2 \times 33 = 66$
C_6	$11 \times 3 = 33$	2	$2 \times 33 = 66$
C_7	$7 \times 7 = 49$	2	$2 \times 49 = 98$
$\Sigma_1 = 271$		$\Sigma_2 = 16$	$\Sigma_3 = 632$
$= W$		All edges	$= S_z$

Case of polyphenylenes :

For polyphenylenes, the W and the S_z indices are calculated using the following expressions :

$$W = 24h^3 + 3h \quad (9)$$

$$S_z = 6h(7h^2 + 2) \quad (10)$$

For polyphenylenes, P_3 (Fig. 6), we obtain $W = 657$ and $S_z = 1170$. Estimation of these values using our method is illustrated in Fig. 6.

Fig. 6. All cuts of polyphenylenes P_3 .

Elementary cut C	$n(B').n(B'')$	r	$r.n(B').n(B'')$
C_1	$3 \times 15 = 45$	2	$2 \times 45 = 90$
C_2	$3 \times 15 = 45$	2	$2 \times 45 = 90$
C_3	$3 \times 15 = 45$	2	$2 \times 45 = 90$
C_4	$6 \times 12 = 72$	1	$1 \times 72 = 72$
C_5	$9 \times 9 = 81$	2	$2 \times 81 = 162$
C_6	$9 \times 9 = 81$	2	$2 \times 81 = 162$
C_7	$9 \times 9 = 81$	2	$2 \times 81 = 162$
C_8	$12 \times 6 = 72$	1	$1 \times 72 = 72$
C_9	$15 \times 3 = 45$	2	$2 \times 45 = 90$
C_{10}	$15 \times 3 = 45$	2	$2 \times 45 = 90$
C_{11}	$15 \times 3 = 45$	2	$2 \times 45 = 90$
$\Sigma_1 = 657$		$\Sigma_2 = 20$	$\Sigma_3 = 1170$
$= W$		All edges	$= S_z$

Case of helicenes :

The W and the S_z indices of helicene are calculated from the following expressions :

$$W = 1/3 (8h^3 + 72h^2 - 26h + 27) \quad (7)$$

$$S_z = 1/3 (16h^3 + 204h^2 - 157h + 99) \quad (8)$$

Use of these expressions for helicene H_4 (Fig. 5) gives $W = 529$ and $S_z = 1253$ respectively. Same values for W and S_z for H_4 are obtained by our method as illustrated below :

Fig. 5. All cuts of helicene H_4 .

Case of monocyclic graph with tree-like side chains :

Gutman and coworkers¹⁵ have given the following expression for the calculation of W and S_z indices of monocyclic graphs with tree-like side chains :

Fig. 7. The structure of the graph $C_n [T_1, T_2, \dots, T_n]$ respectively monocyclic molecules.

$$W = \sum_{i=1}^n W(T_i) + \sum_{i=1}^n (|M| - |T_i|) d(r_i / T_i) + \frac{1}{2} \sum_{i=1}^n \sum_{j=1}^n |T_i| |T_j| d(v_i, v_j) C_n \quad (11)$$

$$S_z = \sum_{i=1}^n W(T_i) + \sum_{i=1}^n (|M| - |T_i|) d(r_i / T_i) + \frac{1}{2} \sum_{i=1}^n \sum_{j=1}^n |T_i| |T_j| d(v_i, v_j) C_n - \delta(n) \sum_{i < j} |T_i| |T_j| \quad (12)$$

The details of these expressions are available in Ref. 15.

The methodology used by us for calculating W and S_z indices of polyphenylenes helped us to provide a simple method for the calculation of these indices for monocyclic graphs containing tree-like side chains. We illustrate this by taking the examples of graphs presented in Figs. 8 and 9. The Fig. 8 is the carbon-hydrogen suppressed graph of salicylhydroxamic acid (SHA), while the latter is the all-hydrogen suppressed graph of SHA. The SHA and its nuclear substituted derivatives exhibit several physiological activities including antitumor activity¹⁶⁻²⁰. The SHA moiety has the following molecular structure :

Molecular structure of SHA

Fig. 8. All cuts of carbon-hydrogen suppressed molecular graph of SHA.

Elementary cut C	$n(B') \cdot n(B'')$	r	$r \cdot n(B') \cdot n(B'')$
C_1	$3 \times 11 = 33$	2	$2 \times 33 = 66$
C_2	$3 \times 11 = 33$	2	$2 \times 33 = 66$
C_3	$5 \times 9 = 45$	2	$2 \times 45 = 90$
C_4	$1 \times 13 = 13$	1	$1 \times 13 = 13$
C_5	$2 \times 12 = 24$	1	$1 \times 24 = 24$
C_6	$8 \times 6 = 48$	1	$1 \times 48 = 48$
C_7	$13 \times 1 = 13$	1	$1 \times 13 = 13$
C_8	$10 \times 4 = 40$	1	$1 \times 40 = 40$
C_9	$12 \times 2 = 24$	1	$1 \times 24 = 24$
C_{10}	$13 \times 1 = 13$	1	$1 \times 13 = 13$
C_{11}	$13 \times 1 = 13$	1	$1 \times 13 = 13$
$\Sigma_1 = 299$		$\Sigma_2 = 14$	$\Sigma_3 = 410$
$= W$		All edges	$= S_z$

We now consider all hydrogen-suppressed graph of SHA.

Fig. 9. All cuts of all-hydrogen suppressed graph of SHA

Elementary cut C	$n(B') \cdot n(B'')$	r	$r \cdot n(B') \cdot n(B'')$
C_1	$3 \times 8 = 24$	2	$2 \times 24 = 48$
C_2	$3 \times 8 = 24$	2	$2 \times 24 = 48$
C_3	$4 \times 7 = 28$	2	$2 \times 28 = 56$
C_4	$1 \times 10 = 10$	1	$1 \times 10 = 10$
C_5	$7 \times 4 = 28$	1	$1 \times 28 = 28$
C_6	$9 \times 2 = 18$	1	$1 \times 18 = 18$
C_7	$10 \times 1 = 10$	1	$1 \times 10 = 10$
C_8	$10 \times 1 = 10$	1	$1 \times 10 = 10$
$\Sigma_1 = 152$		$\Sigma_2 = 11$	$\Sigma_3 = 228$
$= W$		All edges	$= S_z$

Conclusions :

From the above results and discussion we conclude that our methodology is the simplest method for simultaneous calculations of W and S_z indices of benzenoid systems as well as of systems consisting of monocycles containing tree-like side chains.

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